

RHEOLOGICAL BEHAVIOR OF SiC/Al COMPOSITES

Ph. Jarry, W. Loué, J. Bouvaist
Centre de Recherches CEGEDUR PECHINEY,
BP 27, 38340 VOREPPE (France).

ABSTRACT

In order to forge or extrude discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites, knowledge of their rheological properties is necessary. A wide range of strain-rates and temperatures has been explored for various discontinuous SiC reinforced Aluminum alloy composites. Several material parameters have been taken into account such as reinforcement size and morphology. Correlations for flow data were deduced from hot torsion and traction tests, and their physical meaning is discussed.

Strain rate sensitivity of the composites is modified when compared with the matrix, and a strong increase in the activation energy is observed. Scanning electron microscopy fractography has been carried out. Underlying micro-mechanisms are suggested.

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of rheological properties of SiC whisker - or SiC particle reinforced aluminum composites is interesting from several points of view:

- to choose the optimal temperature vs strain-rate window in order to shape these composites
- to compare the reinforcing potentials of whiskers and particles (which is economically relevant)
- to shed light onto the strengthening mechanisms of these materials at elevated temperatures.

From a purely mechanical point of view, the introduction of refractory particles or whiskers into a metallic matrix should reduce the creep rate at a given stress [1,2]. A reduction of two orders of magnitude on the creep rate is predicted and observed for whisker-reinforced aluminum matrix composites.

However such models cannot take into account the metallurgical micro-mechanisms that govern deformation at elevated temperature. It is the aim of this paper to give insight into this problem.

EXPERIMENT**MATERIALS:**

The materials studied in this program was 2124 aluminum reinforced with 25% vol. SiC whiskers or particles, elaborated by powder metallurgy by ARCO, and extruded at Pechiney facilities in the form of bars of diameter 20 mm (extrusion ratio = 53).

After extrusion, the whiskers' mean aspect ratio was 7. The particle size was about 4 μm . In both cases the scatter of the size distributions was very important.

All samples' axes were parallel to the extrusion direction.

CHARACTERIZATION AT ROOM TEMPERATURE:**Microstructure**

In the extruded state, the microstructure of these materials is characterized by a very fine grain size (of the order of one micron in diameter) corresponding to the average distance between whiskers or particles. The whiskers are well aligned with the extrusion direction. The metal grains are slightly elongated in the extrusion direction, but their aspect ratio is less than 3. The microstructure exhibits a strong internal strain hardening, even after annealing of the extrusion hardening, and quenching, as evidenced by X-Ray diffraction. It is the evidence of a strong strain hardening due to the different thermal contractions of SiC and Al during quenching.

Furthermore, such discrepancies in thermal expansions are likely to induce residual stresses in the matrix.

The various sources of strengthening at room temperature: fibrous strengthening, strain hardening during quenching due to the CTE mismatch, structural precipitation, lead to mechanical properties that are listed below in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Mechanical Properties at Room Temperature:

		YS (MPa)	TS (MPa)	e%	E (GPa)
2024	T4	400	530	13	75
2124 + SiCw	T4	587	770	0,7	110
2124 + SiCp	T4	421	524	1,2	

TESTS:

The rheology was studied through hot tension and hot torsion tests in order to explore a broad range of temperatures and strain-rates. All test samples were homogenized prior to the test and then held at the test temperature for one hour before starting the test.

Temperature realm : 375°C to 495°C

Strain rate range: tension : 4.10^{-4} s^{-1} to 2.10^{-1} s^{-1} ; torsion : 3.10^{-2} to 3 s^{-1} .

The samples were 42mm in length and 6mm in diameter for the tensile test and 50mm in length and 9mm in diameter for the torsion test. The torsion

test was conducted at constant length.

The torsion data were studied according to the Field and Backofen method. The flow stress was taken as the maximum value of the stress during the test.

RESULTS

Shape of the Traction and Torsion Curves

The stress-strain curves in traction (Fig.1a) show evidence of some strain softening for both whisker- and particle- reinforced composites.

The torque-twist curves (Fig.1b) obtained from the torsion test, on the other hand, show evidence:

- of a plateau of constant torque and/or some strain softening in the case of particle-reinforced composites
- of some amount of strain hardening in the case of whisker-reinforced composites. This may be due to the changing orientation of the whiskers as they get closer to the principal stress direction (at 45° to the sample axis) thus providing a more efficient reinforcement.

Fig. 1a) Typical Traction Curve for both SiCw/2124 and SiCp/2124

Fig. 1b): Typical Torque - Twist Curves for SiCw/2124 and SiCp/2124

The curves for whisker reinforced composites show some amount of strain hardening, due to the changing orientation of the whiskers during the test.

Iso-Flow-Stress Curves of
25% SiCw/2124

Iso-Flow Stress Curves of
25% SiCp/2124

Iso-Fracture Strain Curves
of 25% SiCw/2124

Iso-Fracture Strain Curves
of 25% SiCp/2124

Fig. 2

Iso-Flow Stress and Iso-Fracture Strain Curves in the $\log \dot{\epsilon}$ vs T plane

TABLE 2: Flow Stresses for (respectively):

$\dot{\epsilon}, T$	in MPa				
	2024 2124 + SiCp 2124 + SiCw	375°C	400°C	450°C	495°C
3 s^{-1}		120	110	80	70
		170	140	90	65
		200	170	130	55
$0,3 \text{ s}^{-1}$		95	90	60	50
		110	90	70	30
		140	120	90	30
$0,05 \text{ s}^{-1}$		70	50	30	20
		70	60	30	10
		100	75	40	10

The comparison was made with a 2024 aluminum, slightly better at elevated temperature than 2124. The increase in performances due to the ceramic reinforcement is thus a *fortiori* confirmed.

As shown in Table 2, whiskers provide a very efficient reinforcement except for the highest temperature 495°C. Particles provide reinforcement, but to a lesser extent, mainly for the lower temperatures and the higher strain-rates.

At 495°C, both whiskers and particles weaken the matrix.

On Fig.2 are shown the iso flow-stress curves in the $\ln \dot{\epsilon}$ vs T plane, as well as the iso-fracture strain curves. The particulate composite exhibits higher fracture strains than the whisker composite. Strain rate has no effect on fracture strain at high temperature for SiCw/2124; the effect of strain rate on fracture strain of SiCp/2124 is totally reversed between the lower and the higher temperatures. Both observations are the sign of a change in the damaging process when temperature increases as confirmed by fractography.

Influence of Strain Rate:

The flow stress increases with increasing strain rates. The $\ln \sigma$ vs $\ln \dot{\epsilon}$ plots are linear for 2024 alone and for reinforced 2124 at low temperatures, but start to exhibit an increase in slope for increasing strain rates at higher temperatures, thus tending towards a superplastic behavior (see Fig.3).

The strain rate sensitivity m is measured on the $\ln \sigma$ vs $\ln \dot{\epsilon}$ plots as: $m = \partial \ln \sigma / \partial \ln \dot{\epsilon}$. This measures the evolution of the microstructure rather than the instantaneous strain rate sensitivity at constant microstructure.

Fig.4 shows the variation of m with temperature for unreinforced 2024 and reinforced 2124. Whiskers and particulates, in this order, provide an increasing increment in the strain rate sensitivity. At 495°C,

SiC_p/2124 exhibits a value of m close to 0.3 which is twice the value for the matrix alone at the same temperature.

Fig. 3:
Influence of Strain Rate
on Flow Stress
a) 2024
b) SiCw/2124
c) SiCp/2124

Fig. 4: Influence of Temperature on Strain Rate Sensitivity

Influence of Temperature:

The dependence of the flow stress on temperature is quite strong (as shown in the $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ curves Fig.5) resulting in a very high apparent activation energy (see Table 3 below).

TABLE 3 : APPARENT ACTIVATION ENERGY

Materials	Apparent Activation Energy	
	at high strain rates (.3 to 3 s ⁻¹)	at low strain rates (4.10 ⁻⁴ to 4.10 ⁻³ s ⁻¹)
2024	120 kJ/mol	
2124 + SiC _w	140 kJ/mol	290 kJ/mol
2124 + SiC _p	220 kJ/mol	≈300 kJ/mol

For reinforced 2124, the slope of the curves (the apparent activation energy Q) increases with decreasing strain rates. For SiC_w/2124 and at high strain rates, Q is not significantly different from that of the matrix evaluated by the same method except for the highest temperature. For all other cases, that is for particle reinforced 2124 and for whisker reinforced 2124 at lower strain rates, Q is over 200kJ/mol. It is higher for particulate composites than for whisker composites. These values are to be compared with 120-140 kJ/mol, a normal value for Aluminum alloys corresponding with the self-diffusion activation energy. Q is even higher near the highest temperature 495°C. This must be related to the fact that at this temperature, the ceramic particles weaken rather than strengthen the matrix giving rise to a new deformation mechanism.

S.E.M. Fractography (Fig.6)

At the lower temperatures, the fracture is ductile, with dimples. Relatively little whisker pull-out is observed which indicates a good interfacial bond. Many whiskers are at the bottom of the dimples, the sign of a classical ductile fracture mechanism by void initiation and growth on the inclusion-matrix interface. A certain number of whiskers are found on top of dimple edges. It is assumed that these whiskers have had bridging functions between the fracture surfaces. Some whiskers show a total decohesion of their interface with the matrix. This is thought to be caused by preferential shear in regions of locally very high whisker concentration or at the edge of whisker free zones.

At the higher temperatures ($\geq 450^\circ\text{C}$) the fracture surface of the whisker composite is clearly intergranular with a lot of whisker exposure. Aluminum grain decohesion is observed; a few whiskers are found to have provided a bridging function, though. A polished longitudinal section of a whisker reinforced sample tested at 450°C reveals an intergranular like damaging process in which not only whiskers, but also big precipitates grown during the exposure a high temperature, act as crack initiators.

Although more difficult to interpret, the failure mechanisms of the particulate composites deduced from the fracture surfaces seem to be the same as for the whisker reinforced composite except for the bridging effect.

Fig. 5:
Influence of Temperature on
Flow Stress and Evaluation of
the Apparent Activation Energy
a) 2024
b) SiCp/2124
c) SiCw/2124

Fig. 6: S.E.M. Fractographies showing on the left the fracture surface of SiCw/2124 after tensile testing at 375°C, and on the right the same material fractured in tension at 495°C. The first one is ductile and the latter is intergranular with some bridging by whiskers.

DISCUSSION

Ceramic reinforced aluminum composites exhibit a strongly altered behavior at high temperature compared with the unreinforced matrix. The principal features of their rheology can be summarized as follows:

- a strong increase in the flow stress as long as the temperature is not too close to the solidus temperature of the alloy,
- a strong dependence of flow stress on strain rate, increasing with higher strain rates. High values of the strain rate sensitivity may be reached, especially at high strain rates and temperatures.
- a strong dependence of flow stress on temperature, resulting in abnormally high values of the apparent activation energy of deformation.

Origin of the Change in Strain Rate Sensitivity:

The particular microstructure of these composites in the extruded state, characterized by a very **fine grain size**, may account for the increase in strain rate sensitivity. It is well known that grain size is the main microstructural factor controlling the ability to superplastic forming of metallic alloys [3].

Another characteristic of these materials is the big difference in coefficients of thermal expansion of the metallic and ceramic phases that give rise to **internal stresses**. These may boost deformation and strain rate sensitivity especially under thermal cycling [4,5]. The existence of such internal stresses is evidenced by the existence of a threshold stress for creep of composites [6].

Origin of the High Values of the Apparent Activation Energy:

It is known that internal stresses resisting high temperature deformation can increase the value of the apparent activation energy. Nardone and Tien [7] have shown that an internal stress σ_R can have a strong influence on the evaluation of the constants that appear in the rheological law, and that the variation of σ_R with σ (the imposed stress), was particularly relevant to explain the drop of the strain rate sensitivity of particulate reinforced alloys in creep experiments. Likewise in our case we can look at the rheological law from the temperature point of view, since the increase in the apparent activation energy is quite dramatic.

Taking a rheological law of the form: $\dot{\epsilon} = A \sigma^{na} \exp(-Q_a/RT)$

where na is the apparent stress sensitivity = $1/ma$, ma is the apparent strain rate sensitivity and Q_a is the apparent activation energy, and:

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A' (\sigma - \sigma_R)^n \exp(-Q_0/RT)$$

in the presence of a resisting internal stress σ_R , Q_0 being the actual activation energy, leads to [6,8]:

$$Q_a = Q_0 - (d\sigma_R/dT) nRT^2 / (\sigma - \sigma_R)$$

The variation of the internal stress with temperature may well be the principal cause for the high value of the apparent activation energy. The fact that the highest values of Q_a are observed with particles rather than with whiskers tends to confirm this assumption, since the internal stress is likely to drop rapidly with temperature in the case of

particulates due to the lack of load transfer. Likewise, the highest values of Q_a are observed in the case of 2124 matrix composites, at the highest temperatures when intergranular failure has been observed, corresponding with a total drop of the internal stress by failure of the interfaces that would transfer it to the matrix. The fact that higher values of Q_a are observed for lower strain rates (see Table 3) is due to the fact that σ is then closer to σ_R making the denominator $(\sigma - \sigma_R)$ decrease. It is a form of the equivalence between decreasing strain rates and increasing temperatures.

So, the temperature dependence of the resiting stress may well explain the change in slope of the $\log \sigma$ vs $(1/T)$ curves (Fig.5) and the higher value of Q_a for particle composites. On the other hand the current value of the resiting stress is significant in explaining the change in slope of the $\log \sigma$ vs $\log \dot{\epsilon}$ curves in Fig.3, that is the increase in the strain rate sensitivity (the decrease of stress sensitivity) when going away from the low stress and low strain-rates realm.

Microstructural Approach:

Until now our approach to the problem has been somewhat phenomenological. Another way of describing the problem is to suggest possible micromechanisms at the level of the micro-structure that may account for the observations. The problem can be posed this way: in spite of ceramic reinforcement whose purpose is to increase the resistance to deformation at elevated temperatures, a tendency towards superplasticity appears. How?

First, the presence of ceramic particles or whiskers induces a very small ($\approx 1\mu\text{m}$) and stable grain size (through their mean spacing and their antirecrystallization power). This small grain size may have several consequences on the rheological behavior: at the lower strain rates, it provides an easier recovery of the microstructure, because of the higher grain-boundary area/grain-volume ratio. Likewise it increases the level of the strain rate for which the transition from a grain boundary sliding and diffusional creep mechanism to a dislocation glide mechanism occurs. This transition is associated with a rapid increase in the flow stress, resulting in a high strain rate sensitivity. It seems that this transition starts to occur in the case of composites (see Fig.3).

Secondly, the stress triaxiality resulting from the presence of inclusions, that is the appearance of a negative hydrostatic pressure of the order of the flow stress modifies the concentration of vacancies as shown by a simple calculation [9]. The vacancy concentration C is of the form: $C \approx A \exp(-\Delta H/kT)$. Now, $\Delta H = U + p\Delta V$, ΔV being the volume generated by the creation of a vacancy, $\Delta V \approx b^3$, (b is the Burgers vector). The occurrence of a negative pressure $-\Delta P$ modifies the vacancy concentration by a factor of $\exp[\Delta P b^3/kT]$. An order of magnitude of ΔP is 100 MPa under high stress triaxiality at 250°C; taking $b=4.1\text{\AA}$, and $T=523\text{K}$ (250°C) gives a factor of 2.6. The vacancy concentration may be more than doubled because of the presence of hard particles. This tends to make possible a further occurrence of diffusional mechanisms and thus acts in favor of the transition towards superplasticity initiated by the fine grain size. This effect should be more important in the case of particles

than in the case of whiskers, because particles cause more stress concentration than whiskers do [10].

However ceramic inclusions also prevent the metal grains from deforming by imposing a resisting stress to them. On a microscopic level, it means that the interfaces which are put under less tensile stress are not good sources for vacancies, resulting in a threshold stress (observed in creep experiments). This effect should be more important in the case of whiskers, since they are subject to more stress transfer. It may also result in an activation barrier for emission of vacancies, partially accounting for the apparent increase in activation energy.

This brief survey of possible micromechanisms is consistent with observations. Particle composites exhibit a higher strain rate sensitivity than whisker composites with almost the same grain size, which is consistent with a possible influence of stress triaxiality and the lower value of the resisting internal stress. They exhibit a higher apparent activation energy, consistent with the fact that the resisting stress collapses rapidly when temperature increases, due to the lack of load transfer in the case of particles.

CONCLUSION

Discontinuously reinforced aluminum composites have been tested at elevated temperature. They exhibit higher flow stresses than the matrix, except for the highest studied temperature at which intergranular failure occurs. Whiskers provide a better reinforcement than particles. Whiskers, and particles even more, induce an increase in the strain rate sensitivity and the apparent activation energy. These features are well explained by the existence of internal stresses that resist deformation and by the complex triaxial state of stress due to the presence of stress concentrating ceramic phases.

A tendency towards superplasticity is confirmed at high strain rates that could lead to new shaping conditions of these materials relatively to their matrices.

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REFERENCES

- [1] KELLY and STREET "Creep of Discontinuous Fibre Composites", Proc. Royal Soc. London 328 A (1972).
- [2] McLEAN, "Modeling of Creep Deformation in MMC's" Conference Proceedings, ICMV, San Diego (1985) Warendale AIME.

- [3] WERT: "Grain Refinement and Grain Size Control in Superplastic Forming", J. of Metals, Sept.1982.
- [4] WU and SHERBY, "Superplasticity in SiC Whisker Reinforced Aluminium Alloy", Scripta Met, Vol. 18, pp 773 - 776, 1984.
- [5] DERBY, "Internal Superplasticity in MMC's", Scripta Met., 19 (6), (1985) pp703-707.
- [6] McLEAN: "Threshold Stress for Dislocation Creep" Acta Met. Vol.33, N°4 (1985) pp 545-556
- [7] NARDONE and TIEN, "On the Creep Rate Dependence of Particle Strengthened Alloys" Scripta Met., Vol.20, (1986) 797-802.
- [8] PURUSHOTAMAN and TIEN, Acta Met. 26, (1978), 519.
- [9] McCLINTOCK and ARGON, Mechanical Behavior of Materials, MIT (1966) p.150.
- [10] ELDIWANY and WHEELER "On Rigid Inclusions of Minimum Stress Concentrations" J. Mech. Phys. Solids vol 34 N°1 (1986) pp 19-28